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Finding Endometriosis using Machine Learning:

FEMaLe

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Legislation

Legislation H2020 Framework Programme – Regulation (EU) No 1291/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 December 2013 establishing Horizon 2020 - The Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (2014-2020) (OJ 347, 20.12.2013, p. 104).

Euratom Research and Training Programme (2014-2018) – Council Regulation (Euratom) No 1314/2013 of 16 December 2013 on the Research and Training Programme of the European Atomic Energy Community (2014-2018) complementing the Horizon 2020 – The Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (OJ L 347, 20.12.2013, p. 948).

H2020 Specific Programme – Council Decision 2013/743/EU of 3 December 2013 establishing the Specific Programme Implementing Horizon 2020 - The Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (2014-2020) (OJ L 347, 20.12.2013, p. 965).

Rules for Participation (RfP) – Regulation (EU) No 1290/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 of December 2013 laying down the rules for the participation and dissemination in Horizon 2020 – the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (2014-2020) (OJ L 347, 20.12.2013, p.81).

Financial Regulation (FR) – Regulation (EC, Euratom) No 966/2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 October 2012 on the financial rules applicable to the general budget of the European Union (OJ L 298, 26.10.2012, p.1).

Rules of Application (RAP) – Commission Regulation (EC, Euratom) No 1268/2012 of 29 October 2012 on the rules of application of Regulation (EC, Euratom) No 966/2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council on the financial rules applicable to the general budget of the Union (OJ L 298, 26.10.2012, p.1).

1. IMPACT CORRESPONDS TO VALUE CREATION

Traditionally, impact has been viewed as a result of the deliverables. Impact is therefore assumed to be realized *after* the deliverables have been delivered. For instance, new organizational approaches, new procedures, and a new IT system will result in shorter lead times and fewer mistakes.

In contrast, *Half Double* focuses on the flow of impact throughout the entire duration of the project. The FEMaLe project's impact can and should be defined initially and realized at different points during the process. In this context, **impact corresponds to value creation**, which again describes the relative relationship between both benefits and costs.

The ultimate success criterion from this perspective is stakeholder satisfaction. Each stakeholder's subjective perception of the project influences the pace of behavioral change, commitment to new solutions from the rest of the value chain, and whether our solution succeeds in the market. In effect, the project can deliver perfectly on the business case but still fail to live up to expectations, because the expectations have changed over time.

Therefore, there is a higher degree of complexity. Impact becomes a multidimensional, strategic concept requiring that we always consider the points of view of the different stakeholders. Needs that constantly change over time due to contextual turbulence such as competitor behavior, new legislation, market trends, conflicts, and new roles and preferences, as well as effects that do not materialize until long after the project has been concluded.

Consequently, it is important to keep the following questions in mind: *Who is the FEMaLe customer? Who is the FEMaLe end user? What creates value for them? What can FEMaLe offer that underpins the advantages that the users experience while also minimizing the disadvantages?* The most successful projects constantly follow up on both deliverable and customer value. In terms of customer value, this can be tested well in advance before the final solution is operationalized. The customer can simply test prototypes so that the product is based on genuine user feedback and not merely on internal assumptions about user needs.

Two aspects of Impact Monitoring and Assessment (IMA)

Observation (monitoring) may refer to observing a situation for any changes that may occur over time – to be aware of the state of a system – whereas interpretation (assessment) deals with the changing context and the implications and consequences for the project. A combination of both aspects provides a useful instrument for *FEMaLe Quality Control*, as described in the Deliverable 10.2, *Finding Endometriosis using Machine Learning, 2021: Progress Reporting and Quality Control MI-M4*, Section 7: FEMaLe Quality Control. Monitoring should be done 'objectively' to establish an information base, whereas assessment involves the 'subjective' judgement of different stakeholders in accordance with their individual perceptions. The overall model of IMA in FEMaLe is already outlined in Deliverable 1.1, *Project impact action strategy (PIAS)*.

FEMaLe Impact Monitoring and Assessment

This document focuses on FEMaLe's self-evaluated IMA: an integrated instrument of reflection and learning for quality control throughout the project's whole life cycle to constantly improve actions and activities. It deals with how to operationalize the Half Double-inspired model and will guide all 16 FEMaLe Consortium Beneficiaries as regards IMA activities carried out throughout the project period. Furthermore, the document can help current stakeholders and future parties interested in similar areas to FEMaLe understanding what sort of methods are likely to achieve the best impact for a given action.

2. COMMITMENT TO FEMALE IMPACT METHODS

1. Use the FEMaLe impact case to drive behavioural change and impact

In the beginning of the project, we define a hierarchy of goals for the desired FEMaLe impacts. We then ask ourselves which key stakeholders need to change their behavior to realize the aspired impact, and we define the behavioral impact which the FEMaLe project needs to address. We define few, but critical leading and lagging key performance indicators to track and ensure an ongoing flow of impact realization throughout the FEMaLe project's lifecycle.

2. Design FEMaLe to deliver impact as soon as possible with the FEMaLe end users close to the solution

In close collaboration with FEMaLe users, customers, and other key stakeholders, we design the project to realize impact-driven solutions faster. Through five key workshops and with the help of seven defined roles, a core idea to reduce time to impact is identified, the project organization is designed, and an overall road map for impact realization is in place with key stakeholders committed — right from the start.

3. Check the pulse of key FEMaLe stakeholders on a monthly basis

Key stakeholders are identified through the Impact Solution Design process (2). Key stakeholders expect various impacts to be realized at different points in the project process. Therefore, we initiate and continuously check the pulse of the project management team, the project owner, the executive committee, the end users, the special advisers, and others involved in the FEMaLe project's process and/or impact.

3. DRIVING FEMALE IMPACT METHODS

1A. Build FEMaLe Impact Case to drive behavioural change, stakeholder satisfaction, and impact

Purpose and description

A project is a pitch into the future. You no longer want 'business as usual'. Instead, you seek to create something completely new; a change that will impact your surroundings. Projects that define the desired impact and continuously measure and follow up on impact realization throughout the lifetime of the project are more successful.

The Half Double methodology's primary focus is therefore on impact rather than on deliverables. We encourage the project leader, project owner, project team, and everybody with a critical stake in the project to establish a common understanding of the impact the project is intended to create – from day one. The project owner and the team also need to continuously measure and track impact realization. Without the right focus, we risk creating a new product, service, or process that is perfect in every way, but that ends up being discarded by the very users, employees, or customers it was created to satisfy.

Show how the project creates a chain of results and finally, the intended outcomes

In classic project management literature, the project manager is responsible for deliverables, and the project owner is responsible for impacts. This is because the project is viewed as a temporary organization, and the impacts are realized after the output is handed over to operations. However, research and experience show significant benefits from acknowledging the change task inherent in any project and making accommodations for it in the initial project and planning sessions. In terms of how to frame and capture a holistic understanding of a project, inspiration can be drawn from program theory. Program theory describes the following transitions from deliverables to impact: establishing deliverables, developing competences, managing change, and realizing benefits. The further we go to the right on this line, the more we remove ourselves from traditional project management. We believe the project should be able to go all the way.

The aim of the **Impact Case** is to describe this journey and summarize the last four steps shown in the figure below. The first step — new behavior — requires the employees to be satisfied and accept the new form of working so that they use the deliverables and their new competences. The immediate impact is often internal process improvement that creates greater satisfaction between managers and internal customers. Medium-term impact can be greater customer satisfaction, resulting in higher revenue, creating the long-term impact that generates greater satisfaction with top executives and shareholders.

It is this series of stakeholder satisfaction which is the project's overall impact case. It serves as a strong alignment and communication tool that easily and clearly describes the changes needed to achieve the desired impact. We strongly recommend having an active project owner who owns the impact case and ensures a consistent focus on it for the entire duration of the project and after project completion.

1B. Three-step approach

1. Defining the impact case

At the very beginning of the project, we create the impact case. This is a road map of the project's business and behavioral impacts that basically helps establish a common understanding of the impacts targeted by the project and their logical interdependence. This, in turn, helps us identify the most critical deliverables to focus on ensuring early and ongoing impact realization.

The impact question to ask: *What are the value drivers justifying the initiation of this project?*

The impacts list the performance outcome(s) and often consist of targets such as increased stakeholder satisfaction, enhanced customer performance, financial performance, process performance, and compliance with external requirements. It also includes case intangibles such as monetary value in complex change projects, which can be difficult to estimate.

The impact question to ask: *What specific new behaviors do we need to see in practice to drive and sustain the business impacts?*

The behavioral impacts refer to the changes we need to see in people's behavior to initiate, drive, and sustain the change. Targets might be applying specific practices, demonstrating organizational capabilities, technological capabilities, or a demonstrable increase in the employees' competences, knowledge, and abilities. These impacts are broken down into selected Impact Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to navigate the project going forward. The impact case and KPIs are used to follow up on the project progress and continuously adapt plans and efforts to enhance stakeholder satisfaction.

2. Building the Impact Case

When defining the project impacts, it is crucial that everyone starts out by being clear on the answers to the following: Who are the project's key customers? Who are the end users? What creates value for the target group?

3. After the discussion, the following process is initiated

1. Build a hierarchy of purposes and main deliverables in collaboration with the project owner, select subject matter experts, and key stakeholders.
2. Identify the FEMaLe impacts referring to the hierarchy by asking: 'What impact is needed?' and 'What organizational needs must be met for FEMaLe to be considered a success?'
3. Identify the behavioral changes needed to realize each impact by asking: 'What will customers, leaders, and employees be doing differently/better during and after FEMaLe?' and 'Who will be the first to notice, and what will they see?'
4. Identify the most critical impacts to aim for by asking: 'How can we measure or determine if this has the desired impact?' To minimize complexity and maintain focus, the result should preferably be no more than four key impacts.
5. Use the KPIs to guide focus for early impact realization and follow up on them monthly.
6. Invite stakeholders from upper management to the visual project room to discuss, validate, and obtain commitments to the Impact Case on an ongoing basis.

Use the Impact case to drive **behavioral change** and **impact**

FEMaLe
Let's make life better

2A. Design FEMaLe to deliver impact as quickly as possible

Purpose and description

We need to move away from the premise that projects only generate value at the very end of their lifespan. Instead, we need to understand projects as delivering a flow of impacts for their entire duration. To do this, we initiate our projects with a high degree of stakeholder involvement to front-load insights and gain commitment early on.

During project initiation, we establish a strong link between the project, the organization's interest, and the management's interest by focusing on value creation. We design our projects to create iterative feedback loops and to launch minimum viable products for each sprint to pave the way for continuous learning and faster impact realization.

In practice, the process comprises five steps with five specified outputs. The **Impact Solution Design** is the tool we use to facilitate this process every time a project is set in motion. At its core, the impact solution design is a collaborative front-loading process that helps us create an overall road map of the project's value creation from start to finish, which all key stakeholders are aligned on and committed to.

The process is executed by means of workshops with key decision-makers and subject matter experts. During the workshops, questions such as 'What value is the project set in motion to create?' and 'What change will that generate for the key stakeholders and for our organization?' are asked to shift our mindset from thinking in terms of deliverables to thinking in terms of impact.

These are followed by questions such as 'How can we reduce the time it takes to create the behavior needed to realize that value?' and 'How can we design the project to take that idea into practice?'

In the process, we integrate the work we do on the impact case with a strong core idea for reducing the time to the identified impact, an initial project organization, key hypotheses to be validated in the first sprint, and a high-level project plan.

We propose five workshops as a starting point, but the number of workshops needed for each step depends on the project and the situation at hand. This front-loading exercise makes it possible to bring together subject matter experts to work on the project for a shorter, intensive duration. However, the members are not necessarily allocated to the project after the process is concluded. This makes it easier to gain access to these critical resources – as opposed to full-time allocation for the entire duration of the project.

2B. Five steps process

Initiate start-up

Set the objectives of the project. This means the overall purpose, sub-purposes, success criteria, and key deliverables. Identify the key stakeholders to be involved in the impact solution design process. The ideal team consists of the project owner, the project leader. The workshop participants often vary from project to project, but a rule of thumb is to only include the project owner and leader in this initial step.

Build the first draft of the impact case, outlining the key business impacts and behavioral impacts to target. Select the four most critical impacts for monthly tracking and follow-up.

Impact definition

Invite one or two key people with subject matter expertise and/or experience from similar projects, and end user representatives. Get their insights and ideas to refine and validate the impact case. Then take the initial step to design the core idea for early impact creation to get a rough core idea.

The core idea visualizes the project's value creation for the entire duration of the project and answers the question 'When will we first see the impact realized, with what, and for whom?'. The outcome of these discussions is an overall map outlining commercial, behavioral, and technical impacts up to its conclusion date. To identify the core idea for reducing the time to impact, refer to areas such as:

- Product: What is the core use of the product/service/system/process? If we remove all excess 'nice-to-have' features, what would the solution look like? Could we release the core version as a minimum viable product and then build on it?
- Process: How could the process be sliced? Could we break down the development process to reflect the actual end user workflow? Could we deliver part or half of the process for each release?
- People: Which segments should we target specifically first with the first release – any high-impact segments, countries, or end user groups? Can we limit the first release to only focus on that group in order to reduce time to impact? Who can we include early in the process to front-load insight, behavioral change, and stakeholder satisfaction?

Review the stakeholders and add or adapt as needed, identify, and book the solution team for the next workshops and take a mini pulse check to be in touch with your key stakeholders

Impact solution design 1

Use the user representatives and solution teams' expertise to get into detail with the core idea and enrich it with their insights and ideas. Do not fall in love with your initial core idea. Identify the impact, the main deliverables needed to fulfil them and draft a road map for impact creation. Ensure that you deliver impact throughout the project, not just in the end. Assess the risks and risk management plan and take a mini pulse check to be in touch with your key stakeholders.

Impact solution design 2

Validate the impact solution design, create a cost overview, and create a high-level plan and organization needed to realize the impact based on the core idea. Remember to draw on and include methods such as prototyping, fast prototyping, early learning loops, and customer insights. Take a mini pulse check to be in touch with your key stakeholders. Things might have changed through the process and commitment to the plan is essential.

Concluding start-up

Invite the project owner and upper management stakeholders to review and provide feedback on the five outputs of the impact solution design.

Discuss next steps and agree on how to interact going forward, and collect the lessons learnt to accelerate execution. Take a last pulse check to review the commitment from the key stakeholders involved in the workshop. The impact solution design process is about identifying the great core idea to reduce the time to impact. The aim is to figure out how to create value and stakeholder satisfaction fast by going live with valuable elements of the solution as early as possible.

The impact solution design is an overall roadmap of the project’s value creation from start to finish. It is made to reduce time to impact and enhance early value creation in project execution. The tool is based on the five workshops described, where each will bring an outcome.

3A. Be in touch with the pulse of key FEMaLe stakeholders

Purpose and description

Acknowledging and working actively with the dynamic nature of projects is the key to success. Interests and focus change rapidly, and we need to gain insights and facilitate a continuous dialog among the right people to ensure engagement and continued focus on the right impact. As part of the effort to gain these insights, we identify FEMaLe's key stakeholders, and, once a month, we distribute an electronic questionnaire containing six questions designed to take the stakeholder's 'pulse'.

We ask questions such as: 'Are you confident that your current work is creating impact for FEMaLe?' and 'Do you believe that FEMaLe creates the desired impact?'

The **FEMaLe Pulse Check** report provides a snapshot of how each stakeholder experiences the project. These insights function as a basis for a constructive dialog on how to lead FEMaLe going forward to leverage impact, ensure energizing working conditions and promote personal development. In addition, the Pulse Check results give FEMaLers the opportunity to reach out to selected stakeholders to ask them to elaborate on a particularly high or low score.

The dynamic relation between FEMaLe and its key stakeholders tends to create an open, transparent, and inclusive atmosphere, because it helps ensure that everyone with a stake always feels included and heard.

The Pulse Check is a dialog tool that helps us to ask the right questions to the right people inside and outside of FEMaLe. It is an electronic questionnaire consisting of six questions sent out monthly to key stakeholders to provide the basis for continuous feedback.

Although the pulse check appears to be quite basic in its form, the key to success is to acknowledge that the tool is a change initiative. Meaning that it requires careful consideration and clear communication and alignment. Everybody should have the answer to: 'Why should I bother to engage?', 'How do I do this the right way?', and 'How will the project leader follow up on the results?'. As we realize both behavioral and impact on an ongoing basis, it is essential that we monitor the satisfaction levels of key stakeholders in real time to act and adjust the project process as key insights and learning emerge.

4. CO-CREATING FEMALE IMPACT

The overall FEMaLe Impact Case can be viewed below, co-created by using the online visual collaboration platform Miro (as described in deliverable 9.2 Dissemination Package):

EQuIP (P3) will assist the 10 FEMaLe Work Package (WP) Leaders in co-creating a WP-specific Impact Case in early autumn 2021 to monitor WP impact, after which we will analyse content to guide dialogues between the 10 WP Leaders on how to improve or increase any specific types of impact.

Following, the five Impact Solution Design workshops will be organised and conducted in late autumn 2021. The monthly FEMaLe Pulse Checks will guide both the Impact Case and Impact Solution Design processes.

5. DATA COLLECTION AND DATAFLOW

Dataflow	<p>AU will be responsible for data collection through SurveyXact. EQuIP will use SurveyXact to conduct online, descriptive data analysis, based on the collected data. The results will be shared with the FEMaLe Beneficiaries via the Correlate platform (link to monthly reports).</p> <p>We will discuss whether the results urge any actions or not.</p> <p>The main data of the monthly FEMaLe Pulse Checks will be kept online in SurveyXact.</p> <p>The backup data of the Pulse Checks will be stored at Aarhus University, Bartholins Allé 2, DK-8000 Aarhus, Denmark on an encrypted drive.</p>
The data controllers, project group and project manager	<p>Aarhus University, CVR no. 31119103, is the data controller for the processing of your personal data. The FEMaLe group is responsible for the project (hereinafter referred to as the 'Project Group').</p> <p>The project group is headed by Ulrik Bak Kirk and can be contacted at Bartholins Allé 2, building 1260, room 241, by email (ubk@ph.au.dk) or phone (+45 28 86 438 63).</p>

6. IMPACT MONITORING ACTION PLAN

The FEMaLe Impact Monitoring Action Plan proposes a strategic framework that is highly and structurally embedded in the project’s structure and work plan:

	Activity	JUNE	JULY		AUGUST		SEPT		OCT		NOV		DEC		Lead
		1-30	1-15	16-31	1-15	16-30	1-15	16-31	1-15	16-30	1-15	16-31	1-15	16-31	
1	All FEMaLe partners have signed informed consent before Pulse Checks.														All FEMaLe Beneficiaries
2	Circulate the Pulse Check questionnaire to the key stakeholders.														Lead: AU
3	Analyse Pulse Check data and regular reporting.														Lead: EQUIP
3	All WP Leaders complete Impact Case for all 10 WPs. Impact Cases will be shared in a continuously updated overview document and will be used to complete IMA reports every six months.														Lead: EQUIP
4	Impact Solution Design workshops.														Lead: EQUIP
5	Prepare and complete the deliverables 1.3 and 1.4.			D1.3									D1.4		Lead: EQUIP
6	Co-creation of the FEMaLe Impact Monitoring and Assessment activities to start on 1 January 2022.														Lead: EQUIP

7. FEMALE IMPACT FACILITATORS & MULTIPLIERS

FEMaLe has formed its initial group of 10 experts to observe and discuss issues of local, regional, and national significance, corresponding to the project's research and innovation environments. The group of specialists is composed of agents of the medical sphere and the civil society as well, representing different positions in the health care arena. The expert group consists of five male and five female members so far.

Facilitator	Sex	WP	Impact	Affiliation
Per Svejvig , Associate Professor	M	1	Virtual Project Management and Value Creation	The Half Double Institute
Thomas Kristian Ruth , Senior Management Consultant	M	1	Half Double Methodology	Implement Consulting Group
Louise Dreisig , Journalist	F	1,2,9	The best Danish resource of endometriosis information.	Endometriosis Denmark (DEN)
Bianca De Bie, Chair	F	1,2,9	+6k followers on Facebook +1,2k followers on Twitter +1,7k followers on Instagram	Endometriose Stichting (NL)
Martin Götte , Professor	M	4,9	Close collaboration with the TREND0 project.	Confirmed member of the FEMaLe Advisory Board.
Louise Hull , Associate Professor	F	5,6,7	Close collaboration with the IMAGENDO project.	Confirmed member of the FEMaLe Advisory Board.
Francesco Mureddu , Director	M	1,2,9	Economic Competitiveness and Social Renewal.	Confirmed member of the FEMaLe Advisory Board.
Dorthe Hartwell , Senior Hospital Physician	F	6,7	Director of Endometriosis Clinic at Rigshospitalet.	Confirmed member of the FEMaLe Advisory Board.
Jette Led Sørensen , Clinical Professor	F	6,7	Procedures for Simulation in Obstetrics and Gynaecology	Confirmed member of the FEMaLe Advisory Board.
Harald Krentel, Dr. med.	M	1,9	President of the European Endometriosis League (EEL)	Confirmed member of the FEMaLe Advisory Board.